

Differences and Similarities between Arabic and Tamil Languages: A Comparative Study

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18517955

Abstract:

The current study aims to present a comprehensive comparative analysis of Arabic and Tamil, two ancient and culturally significant languages belonging to the Semitic and Dravidian language families, respectively. Adapting a qualitative comparative methodology, the research systematically examines the typological differences and similarities across the phonological, morphological, and syntactic domains of both languages. It is based on a linguistic theory that the researcher used books, articles, theses, and website articles to obtain the necessary secondary data. Moreover, the study talks about the unique linguistic synthesis that gave rise to Arabu-Tamil (Arawi), a hybrid language that emerged over centuries of cultural and religious contact. The study revealed that the two languages are almost entirely different from each other at the levels of sound system, morphology, grammar, syntax, and word order. Conversely, the emergence of Arawi demonstrates a significant historical and sociolinguistic connection, highlighting the capacity for linguistic adaptation and synthesis. This study contributes to comparative linguistics by shedding light on the complex relationship between two major linguistic traditions and the language-contact phenomena that result from them.

Keywords: Arabic, Tamil, comparative analysis, Arabu-Tamil.

Introduction:

Language is considered the primary means of communication among human beings, and over time, no single, exact definition has been found that fully explains what language really is. Different conceptions of the nature of language arise in different contexts and in response to a variety of historical, social, political, scientific, and pedagogical needs. According to Aristotle, language is a speech sound produced by human beings to express their ideas, emotions, thoughts, desires, and feelings. Noam Chomsky (2000) says that language is the inherent capability of native speakers to understand and form grammatical sentences. This definition of language considers sentences as the basis of a language. Sentences may be limited or unlimited in number and made up of only limited components.

Linguistics is the scientific study of language; however, it is different from knowledge of a language. The field of linguistics, like any complex field, encompasses several subfields, including semantics, syntax, morphology, and phonology. While previous studies have explored specific comparative aspects of Arabic and Tamil, such as phonology and morphology, a holistic typological analysis that integrates phonological, morphological, and syntactic domains with the socio-historical emergence of Arabu-Tamil remains less explored. This study aims to fill this specific gap. The central research questions guiding this study are:

1. What are the differences between Tamil and Arabic?
2. What are the similarities between Tamil and Arabic?

Methodology:

The research employs a **qualitative comparative analysis**, focusing on the linguistic structures of Arabic and Tamil. The study is descriptive and analytical, relying exclusively on the data and theoretical frameworks. The comparative method, as described by Lehmann (1993), is a technique for studying the development of languages by comparing features. The study is a **comparative linguistic study** that examines, compares, and contrasts Arabic and Tamil. The focus is on identifying the structural differences and similarities between the two languages across various linguistic levels.

Literature Review:

Scholarly estimates of Tamil and Arabic have characterized both languages as classical and religious, with ancient historical connections in South Asia (Samuel, 2010). It is also considered a classical language, partly due to its historical contact with Arabic in South India and Sri Lanka (Samuel, 2010). Contemporary work on Arabic focuses on the complex phonology of modern standard Arabic and dialect-specific studies (Abushhab, 2015; Kastner, 1981). In addition, the emergence of Arbu-Tamil (Arwi) serves as an important historical link that reflects this synthesis and its necessity for Muslim communities in Tamil-speaking areas, both for religious instruction and social interactions.

Overview of Arabic and Tamil:**1. Arabic Language:**

Arabic is a Semitic language that first emerged in the 1st to 4th centuries CE. It is now the lingua franca of the Arab world, and is considered the religious language of all Muslims. The ISO assigns language codes to 30 varieties of Arabic, including its standard form, Modern Standard Arabic, also known as Literary Arabic, which is a modernized form of Classical Arabic.

This distinction exists primarily among Western linguists.

Arabic is the liturgical language of 1.8 billion Muslims and one of six official languages of the United Nations. All varieties of Arabic are spoken by perhaps as many as 422 million speakers (native and non-native) in the Arab world, making it the fifth-most-spoken language worldwide.

2. Tamil Language:

Tamil (தமிழ் *tamiḷ*) is a classical language and one of the major languages of the Dravidian language family. Spoken predominantly by Tamils in India, Sri Lanka, Malaysia, and Singapore, it has smaller communities of speakers in many other countries as well. As of 1996, it was the eighteenth most spoken language, with over 74 million speakers worldwide. It is one of the official languages of India, Singapore, Malaysia, and Sri Lanka.

Tamil is one of the few living classical languages and has an unbroken literary tradition of over two millennia. The name 'Tamil is an anglicized form of the native name தமிழ் (IPA /t̪ɐmiɻ/). The final letter of the name, usually transcribed as the lowercase **l** or **zh**, is a retroflex r. In phonetic transcriptions, it is usually represented by the retroflex approximant.

Tamil is a member of the Tamil language family, which includes the Irula, Kaikadi, Betta Kurumba, Sholaga, and Yerukula languages.

3. Comparative Analysis:

A comparative study shows how two subjects are similar or different. According to **Pickvance (2005)**, comparative analysis is conducted primarily to explain and better understand the causal processes underlying the creation of an event, feature, or relationship, usually by bringing together variations in the explanatory variable or variables. **Tilly (1984)** distinguishes four types of comparative analysis:

individualizing, universalizing, variation-finding, and encompassing (p. 82).

3.1 Phonology: Acoustical and physiological studies have analyzed Arabic phonology in great detail, with special attention to its consonantal system (Al Ani, 1970). The phonemics of Tamil, on the other hand, are frequently compared with both Dravidian and Indo-Aryan linguistic systems (Arden, 1982). Furthermore, it was found that Arabic-borrowed words in other languages undergo phonological modifications to accommodate the target language's phonetic constraints (Hashemi et al., 2014).

3.2 Morphology and Syntax: Arabic syntax is commonly studied in terms of "Principles and Parameters", where the word order, nouns, verbs, and particles are considered (A-Shra'ae, 2012; Weiss, 1976). Crazy and Ikan (1989) have proposed that Tamil anticipates in participial nouns, adjective clauses, and specific complement markers such as enru "that" and enpatu 'why.

3.3 Orthography: Meeran Pillai (1990) states that the Arabu-Tamil has a distinct writing system in which Arabic was adapted to Tamil phonology.

3.4 Syntax: Arabic syntax frequently emphasizes word order and the classification of parts of speech into nouns, verbs, and particles (A-Shra'ae, 2012; Weiss, 1976). On the other hand, Tamil syntax is characterized by the use of participial nouns, adjective clauses, and specific complement markers such as enru and enpatu (Agesthalingom, 1967; Atwell et al., 2004; Heintz, 2008).

3.5 Cultural Context: Tamil and Arabic cultures are tied to the second-oldest linguistic lineage of human culture. Arabic-Tamil, in the South Indian and Sri Lankan context, has been referred to as a "language as mimicry" (Mahroof, 1993), reflecting the intense entanglement between Islamic religious practice and local Tamil cultural artefacts.

The Arwi language was created to maintain the religious identity of the Muslims in Tamil (Meeran Pillai, 1990; Shahul Hameed, 2003). Social Linguistics research in Arabic-speaking countries, such as Jordan, demonstrates how variability becomes a source of cultural resistance to global flows (Al-Ali & Arafa, 2010)—methodological approaches differ depending on the linguistic or social aspect.

3.6 Computational and Corpus Analysis: Speech recognition technology, as well as cross-dialectal data exchange, is used in the analysis of contemporary Arabic to model linguistic processes, serving as a comparative base for Tamil-Arabic (Atwell et al., 2004; Kirchhoff & Vergyri, 2005).

Differences between Tamil and Arabic:

Arabic and Tamil are derived from distinct language families: Semitic and Dravidian, respectively. These differences are evident across all levels of linguistic analysis, including morphology, the consonant and vowel systems, and syntax.

1. Morphology:

Arabic uses an abjad script, a consonantal system in which diacritical marks optionally represent vowels. The script is written from right to left. Arabic uses a root and pattern system; a word's root (usually three consonants) provides the lexical meaning (the root /k-t-b/ combined with the pattern /-i-ā-/ gives kitāb 'book,' whereas the same root combined with the pattern /-ā-i-/ gives kātib 'one who writes' or 'clerk.'). On the other hand, Tamil employs an abugida script, essentially a syllabic system in which distinct symbols represent consonant-vowel combinations. Tamil is written left-to-right.

Arabic words are divided into three mutually exclusive categories that cover all words in the language. The first category is 'noun' /ism/, the second is verbs /fe'l/ and the third is particles

(/harf/). The noun category is vast, covering what English classifies as nouns, pronouns, adjectives, and verbs. Adjectives and adverbs behave exactly like nouns, but undergo inflection for number (singular, dual, plural) and gender (masculine and feminine). For example, the adjective “clever” / ðəki/ can be singularized, dualized/ðəkjən/, and pluralized /ə ðkjə/, as well as masculinized and feminized / ðkjə/. Tamil suffixes include derivational suffixes, which alter part of speech or meaning, and inflectional suffixes, which indicate grammatical categories. Agglutination is extensive, allowing for lengthy words with numerous suffixes, unlike English syntax.

Tamil nouns and pronouns are categorized into two super-classes: "rational" (uyartiṇai) and "irrational" (akṛiṇai), comprising five total classes (paal). "Rational" refers to humans and deities, while "irrational" encompasses all other nouns. "Rational" nouns and pronouns fall into three classes (paal): masculine singular, feminine singular, and rational plural; "irrational" nouns belong to two classes (paal): irrational singular and irrational plural. Suffixes typically denote the class (paal). The plural form of rational nouns can serve as an honorific, gender-neutral singular. In Tamil, adjectives and adverbs are not differentiated; both are categorized under *urichchol*. There are no articles in Tamil; definiteness and indefiniteness are expressed through specific grammatical mechanisms or contextual cues. Tamil distinguishes in the first-person plural between inclusive pronouns நாம் (*nām*) (we), *namathu* (our), which include the addressee, and exclusive pronouns நாங்கள் (*nāṅkaḷ*) (we), *emathu* (our), which do not. This distinction of inclusive and exclusive first-person plural pronouns is also present in several other languages.

2. Sound System:

Arabic and Tamil have a distinctive sound system. Arabic is characterized by a relatively simple vowel system, featuring three short and three long vowels, which are typically / i /, / u /, and / a /, while Tamil possesses a more complex system with five short and five long vowels, in addition to two diphthongs. The consonants show an even deviation. Arabic is rich in sounds that are unusual to Tamil phonology. Arabic has 28 consonants, which fall into the following places of articulation: Labial, Dental, Dental–Alveolar, Palatal, Velar, Uvular, Pharyngeal, and Glottal. The Emphatic coronals (/ s^ʕ /, / d^ʕ /, / t^ʕ /, and / ð^ʕ /) are responsible for causing assimilation of the emphatic to the adjacent non – emphatic coronal consonants (Saiegh-Haddad & Henkin-Roitfarb, 2014). Tamil has 18 consonants, characterized by retroflex and multiple rhotic consonants. Crucially, Tamil does not phonologically distinguish between voiced and unvoiced consonants; voicing is allophonic, determined by a consonant's position in a word, as detailed in the *Tolkāppiyam*. For example, the unvoiced plosive 'p' occurs at the beginning of words, while the voiced plosive 'b' cannot. In the middle of words, unvoiced plosives commonly occur as a geminated pair (e.g., -pp-), while voiced plosives occur after a vowel or a corresponding nasal.

3. Syntax and Word Order:

Arabic grammar (نحو /*naḥw*/) is centered around grammatical inflection, which governs the endings of words to convey the meaning. Arabic has different ways of arranging words in sentences. It has six orders in which words are arranged as a subject, a verb, and a complement. So, Arabic word order can have the following patterns in simple sentences:

VSO, SVO, OVS, OSV, VOS and SOV.

- VSO *ʔakal- a maher-un tuffahat- an.* 'Maher ate an apple.'
eat.pt Maher-Nom apple-Acc
- SVO *Maher- un ʔakal- a tuffahat- an.* 'Maher ate an apple.'
Maher-Nom eat.pt apple-Acc
- OVS *Tuffahat- an ʔakal- a Maher- un.* 'Maher eat an apple.'
Apple-Acc eat.pt Maher-Nom
- VOS *ʔakal-a tuffahat- an Maher- un.* 'Maher ate an apple.'
Eat.pt apple-Acc Maher-Nom
- SOV *Maher- un tuffahat- an ʔakal- a.* 'Maher ate an apple.'
Maher-Nom apple-Acc eat.pt
- OSV *ʔal- tuffahat-u Maher- un ʔakalh- a.* 'Maher ate an apple.'
Apple-Nom Maher-Nom eat.pt

Of these six word-order varieties, three are considered the underlying or representative word orders: VSO, SVO, and VOS (Carroll, 2000). The other three varieties, OVS, OSV and SOV can be derived via transformations.

Tamil is a consistent **head-final language**, with the verb always coming at the end of the clause and a typical word order of Subject-Object-Verb (SOV). Tamil has postpositions rather than prepositions. Tamil is a null-subject language.

a. SOV *raaja meeriyai raaNikku aRimukappaTuttinaan.*

Raja Mary_ACC Rani_DAT introduce_PST-3_

b. *raaja raaNikku meeriyai aRimukam ppaTuttindaan*

c. *meeriyai raaja raaNikku aRimukappaTuttinaan*

d. *meeiyai raaNikku raajaa aRimukappaTuttinaan*

e. *raaNikku raajaa meeriyai aRimukappaTuttinaan*

f. *raaNikku meeriyai aRimukappaTuttinaan*

Nominative is unmarked. -ai and -ukku are case markers representing the accusative and dative cases. The above sentences are identical in logical content but differ in discourse presupposition in a very subtle way. The subject-initial sentence pattern is the most common among the word-order patterns. It was found that sentences with SOV word order occur more frequently than sentences with OSV order. (This is a cross-language characteristic, as observed in

Not all Tamil sentences have subjects, verbs, and objects. It is possible to construct valid sentences that have only a verb - such as *muṭintuviṭṭatu* ("It is completed") - or only a subject and object, such as *atu eṇ vītu* ("That is my house"). Tamil is a verb-final language. Word order in the sentence is relatively free, as long as the sentence ends with a main verb. For example, 'Raja introduced Rani to Mary' in Tamil can have the following word-order variations:

Greenberg 1963, Greenberg's Language Universal. In declarative sentences, the nominal order is almost always one in which the subject precedes the object.) Greenberg's observation is not without exception. There is, however, at least one syntactic argument for hypothesizing that SOV, rather than, say, OSV, represents the underlying word order of Tamil.

Linguistic Synthesis: The Emergence of Arabu-Tamil:

Arawi or Arabu-Tamil:

After discussing the differences between the two languages, there is a combination of Arabic and Tamil in some areas where Tamil is the spoken language. This combination is called "Arawi or Arabu-Tamil".

Arawi, or Arabu-Tamil, is an Arabic-influenced dialect of Tamil written with an extension of the Arabic alphabet and with extensive lexical and phonetic influences from Arabic. Arabu-Tamil is the result of the cultural synthesis between seafaring Arabs and Tamil-speaking Muslims in Tamil Nadu and Sri Lanka, dating back to the 8th century CE.

Arabu Tamil represents the fusion of two great languages, belonging to the great ethnic groups: the Semitic-Arabic and the Dravidian–Tamil. The prevalence of Arabu-Tamil in Colombo, Kayalpattinam, and Kilakarai indicates that it was in use as early as the eighth century of the Christian era. The Arabs and the Tamil Muslims might have played equal roles in the formation of Arabu-Tamil. It is the logical result of the joint efforts of the Arabs and the Tamil Muslims. It originated in the South-West Coast of Ceylon and the South-East Coast of India, more particularly in Kayalpattinam. This language was enriched, promoted, and developed in Kayalpattinam. It rendered a most useful service for the advancement and progress of Arab culture and Tamil culture.

The Arawi script is a testament to linguistic adaptation, and it consists of 40 letters, out of which 28 letters are from Arabic, and 12 additional letters are devised by adding some marks and dots to the original Arabic Alphabet to represent the Tamil vowels and several Tamil consonants that could not be mapped to Arabic

sounds. This adaptation enabled the right-to-left Arabic script to be used to write Tamil.

Literature produced in this language covered the fields of Jurisprudence, Sufism, Law, Medicine, and Poetry. Arabu-Tamil was also used as a bridge language for Tamil Muslims to learn Arabic. Many authentic Hadith manuscripts are produced in this language. Most of the Fiqh books, particularly those of Imaam Shaafi and Imaam Abu Hanifa, are found in Arabu-Tamil.

Today, Arabu-Tamil is of little scholarly interest in parts of Tamil Nadu, India, and Sri Lanka. This literature did not receive much attention in the latter part of the 20th century; languages, such as English, replaced it in many contexts.

Conclusion:

The analysis confirms that Arabic and Tamil share no significant inherent structural similarities at the phonological, morphological, or syntactic levels, which is expected given their distinct origins in the Semitic and Dravidian families. Tamil belongs to the Dravidian language family, and its script is an abugida. It also uses vowel marks to denote vowel sounds in a text. Arabic, on the other hand, is an abjad and does not strictly use vowel marks to denote vowel sounds. The reader has to figure out the pronunciation based on their previous knowledge. However, the emergence of Arabu-Tamil provides a bridge between the two languages, as a script-based, lexically driven synthesis driven by cultural identity. The adaptation of the Arabic abjad to accommodate the Tamil abugida's phonemes by creating 12 new letters is a remarkable example of linguistic engineering motivated by the need for a common means of communication. The extensive borrowing of Arabic vocabulary into Tamil further illustrates the depth of this cultural and commercial exchange. The study confirms that, while there

are fundamental differences between Arabic and Tamil, they share a common point in their cultural and religious history, which manifests in the unique linguistic phenomena of Arawi. This finding validates the use of comparative analysis in uncovering both the structural boundaries and the sociolinguistic bridges between disparate language families.

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